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Author Keywords

"goods-to-person" picking system; Bi-level optimization; genetic algorithm; variable neighborhood search algorithm
(0; 1)-programming; Polyhedral approach; Schedules; Tardiness; Valid inequalities

Abstract

— Beam-hopping (BH) technology, integral to multibeam satellite systems, adapts beam activation to the variable communication demands of terrestrial users. The optimization of power allocation and beam illumination scheduling constitutes the core design challenge in BH systems, especially under the constraint on a limited number of simultaneously active beams due to restricted radio frequency chain availability. This paper proposes a two-stage BH design solution, which minimizes energy consumption in BH satellite communications while accommodating the heterogeneous demands of users. The first stage addresses the coupling variables of power and beam status by recasting

Index Keywords

Wireless telecommunication systems; Backhaul links; Coloring algorithms; QoS guarantee; Scheduling problem; Scheduling schemes; System throughput; Ultra-dense networks; Wireless backhaul; Scheduling

Wireless networks; Active interval; Communication device; Link scheduling; Propagation delays; Rate regions; Real values; Scheduling problem; Short time intervals; Signal propagation delays; Timeslots; Scheduling

Windmill; Energy; Ito process; Layer controls; Multi-timescale control; Power; Time-scales; Two-layer; Two-layer control; Wind power to hydrogen; Hydrogen storage

Year	Document Type	Title	Authors	Source title	Publisher
2017	Conference paper	"critical" Terminology - Apropos of a Conjecture	Vattai, Z.A.	Procedia Engineering	Elsevier Ltd
2021	Article	(1 + ε) ² -and Polynomial-Time Approximation Algorithms for Network Lifetime Maximization with Relay Hop Bounded Connected Target Coverage in WSNs	Nguyen, P.; Ji, Y.; Pham, M.K.; Le, H.; Nguyen, T.H.	IEEE Sensors Journal	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engin
2019	Conference paper	"A based-bee algorithm approach for the multi-mode project scheduling problem"	Niño, K.; Peña, J.	Procedia Manufacturing	Elsevier B.V.
2019	Article	"You have to get wet to learn how to swim" applied to bridging the gap between research into personnel	Petrović, S.	Annals of Operations Research	Springer New York LLC barbara.b.bertram@

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